

Supplementary Material 1: Description of methodology used for equivalence tests.

1. To calculate the mean value (\bar{y}) of the 100 randomly selected y observations (ALS-derived metrics in our case).
2. To subtract \bar{y} from the 100 randomly selected x predictions (DAP-derived metrics in our case) to calculate a shifted regression intercept. This step is necessary for guaranteeing that model shifted intercept and slope are uncorrelated and shall be concurrently tested [41].
3. To establish the regions of equivalence (I) for the slope and the shifted intercept. It is considered as the region around the parameters of a hypothesized model for the perfect similarity between observations and predictions [i.e. slope equals to 1, and shifted intercept equals to mean value of observations (\bar{y})], in which dataset pairs can be considered as equivalents. Given the arbitrariness on the choice of the region of equivalence [40], we opted to test different interval sizes (1, 5, 10, 25, 50 and 75%) so that it was possible to identify the flight was more similar to the ALS data [41]. For illustrative purposes, when considering a region of equivalence of 10% (i.e. 0.1), the regions of equivalence are:
 - a. $I_{slope} = 1 \pm 0.1$, for the slope; and
 - b. $I_{intercept} = \bar{y} \pm (0.1 \times \bar{y})$, for the shifted intercept.
4. To calculate two-sided 97.5% confidence intervals for the slope and the shifted intercept. This step involved the selection of n samples with the replacement of observation pairs (same sample size as the original sample). Subsequently, linear regression models, of bootstrap samples, were fitted using Equation 2 (i.e. DAP-derived metric as the independent variable, and ALS-derived metric as the dependent), and the distribution of slopes and shifted intercepts were calculated. For this, we performed a bootstrap routine with 100 iterations.
5. To test the probability of the shifted intercept distribution confidence intervals to be entirely contained within the region of equivalence for intercept ($I_{intercept}$). If the confidence interval is contained within the region of equivalence, it can be assumed that differences between mean values of datasets are irrelevant. To correct the significance level for the two independent tests (i.e. shifted intercept and slope), we considered $\alpha = 0.025$ so results could be interpreted together. The possible outcomes of this test are:
 - a. The null hypothesis ($\beta_0 \neq \bar{y}$) is rejected, which would indicate that the mean value of a DAP-derived metric is equivalent to the mean value of the ALS-derived; or
 - b. There is insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis (i.e. we could not state that DAP is adequate for estimating the mean value of the ALS-metric).
6. To test the probability of the slope distribution confidence intervals to be entirely contained within the region of equivalence for slope (I_{slope}). As mentioned, the significance level of this test was $\alpha = 0.025$. The possible outcomes of this test are:
 - a. The null hypothesis ($\beta_1 \neq 1$) is rejected, which would indicate that values of a DAP-derived metric have a 1:1 ratio to the values of the ALS-derived; or
 - b. There is insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis (i.e. we could not state that DAP has a 1:1 correlation with ALS-metric).